

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES,
SRINIVAS NAGAR, MUKKA, SURATHKAL,
MANGALORE- 574146

VALUE ADDED COURSE

ON

Diabetic Management

DEPARTMENT OF MEDICAL SURGICAL NURSING

Name of the course:Diabetic Management

Aim of the Course:

The aim of the course is designed to help students to develop knowledge, skill and attitude regarding Diabetes and care.

Objectives of the Course

On completion of the module, the student will be able to

1. understand the concept of NCDs and relevant national programs.
2. review the pathophysiology and clinical diagnostic criteria for diabetes.
3. analyze the diabetes treatment options such as medication, diet, exercise and life style modifications.
4. apply the principles and demonstrate self-management skills to achieve diabetes control .
5. identify onset of complications and provide means of seeking appropriate and timely help.
6. demonstrate understanding of recent updates in diabetes

Duration:

Theory: 30 hours

Practical: 20 hours

Evaluation :

Assessment methods:

- Test paper (Objective test, short answers and case scenario and questions) - 30 marks
- Assessment of assignments/skills - 20 mark

The examination will be conducted by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University

Criteria for eligibility to appear for University Exam

- i.80% attendance in theory
- ii.100% attendance in practical

Criteria for pass

In order to pass a candidate should obtain at least 50% marks aggregate including internal Assessment and marks obtained from college examination

Award of Certificate/Diploma

Certificate will be awarded by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University.

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Abhirami R

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
on "Diabetic Management" from 15/03/2022 to 14/08/2022

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'A.R.', written over a white rectangular background.

Course Coordinator

Dean

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Adithya M P

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Ajina V V

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Albert Joy

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aleena Shibu

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
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Course Coordinator

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Aleesha K S

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Amisha Varghese

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Amrita Francis

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Anamika P

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Anjana M

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Ansu George

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Anusree V C

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Aparna K

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Aswathi K K

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Athira Rajalakshmi

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Bency Baisal

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Beslin George

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Cyriac Manoj Varghese

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Febin Saji

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Gloriya Benny

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Gloriya Shaiju

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Gopika B S

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Harsha K P

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Hellin E

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Hridya Aneesh

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Jaseela M S

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Jithya Saji

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Jyothirmayi K P

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Keerthana K

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Krithika P K

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Layana Mohan

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Mariya Claison

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Namitha Saju

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Merin M Varghese

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Nandana O

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Nikhitha K A

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Nivedhya Sajith

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Parvathy V S

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Pillai Kavya Radhakrishnan

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Course Coordinator

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Punya P K

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Rachel Shiju

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Course Coordinator

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Rinsu Abraham

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Course Coordinator

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sandra Mathew

II Year BSc Nursing has successfully 30 hours of value added course
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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Shikha Krishna P

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Sneha Sukumaran

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COURSE COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **Sreya Theresa Sebastian**

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Sreya V V

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Swathymol V S

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Theertha C

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms

Rithu Mary Thomas

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